

A Novel Secret Key Generation Algorithm for Secure Wireless Communications

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Abstract—The rapid technological advancements in wireless networks have resulted in tremendous increase in the number of connected user and machine-type wireless devices. Physical Layer Security (PLS) has a strong potential for providing security to wireless links in massively connected future wireless networks. The key-based PLS methods aim at generating secret key bits for data encryption/decryption at the legitimate communication nodes by exploiting the randomness inherent in wireless channels. This work proposes a novel secret key-bits extraction algorithm named Moving-Window Wrapped-Envelope Secret Key Generation (MWWE-SKG). The proposed algorithm uses first-order statistics from a sliding temporal window of channel samples to select the channel quantization interval for each window from circularly wrapped channel envelope samples. The differences in hardware noise conditions at the legitimate nodes lead to differences in the measurement of ideally reciprocal channels, which further leads to a mismatch in the generated secret key bits, whereas the channel statistics of the same links are more likely to remain unchanged for a reasonably large length of time window over the channel samples. An extensive analysis on the performance of the proposed algorithm is conducted, where the proposed algorithm is observed to provide a promising trade-off between the critical SKG performance metrics namely the Key Generation Rate (KGR), Bit Mismatch Probability (BMP), and the Key Randomness Property (KRP). Furthermore, a comparative performance analysis of the proposed algorithm with other notable techniques is also conducted to demonstrate the superior performance of the proposed algorithm.

Index Terms—5G, B5G, physical layer, secret key generation, security

I. INTRODUCTION

The 5th Generation (5G) of wireless networks has offered several innovative services such as Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC), and Massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC) [1, 2]. These technological innovations are also facilitating the escalating number of wirelessly connected devices thus increasing the challenges for designing wireless networks with secure links [2]. The broadcast nature of wireless links makes them vulnerable to eavesdropping, while the ultimate goal of security protocols is to ensure a successful exchange of information between legitimate nodes without any leakage of information to the unintended receivers. There exist several cryptographic

methods such as public key cryptography that are employed at the communications layers higher than the physical layer [3, 4]. However, these methods utilize two public and private keys, where the public key is used for encryption and it is shared across entire network, while the private key is used for information decryption by the intended/target receiver [5].

Key-based Physical Layer Security (PLS) is an emerging paradigm for securing wireless links, which avoids the need for the exchange of secret keys between legitimate nodes by exploiting some characteristic observable at the Physical Layer (PHY) of the protocol stack. Secret key generation (SKG) is a PLS scheme in which symmetric key bits are generated simultaneously at a pair of legitimate nodes by exploiting characteristics of their common channel. This procedure eliminates the need for exchanging secret keys and making the communication less vulnerable to eavesdropping. Some SKG methods and their key performance metrics are discussed in [6]. These include the Key Generation Rate (KGR), Bit Mismatch Probability (BMP), and Key Randomness Property (KRP). The foremost target for the independently generated key bits at the legitimate nodes is to obtain a high number of identical key bits relative to the number of channel samples, which also have good randomness properties.

In [7], two SKG methods are proposed. First, a Level Crossing (LC) SKG approach for Rayleigh and Rice fading environments is proposed that contains a self-authentication mechanism. The same work also proposes a second method for general channel conditions which do not explicitly exhibit symmetry in channel distribution, for which a heuristic log-likelihood ratio estimation is employed for SKG. A low complexity SKG method for energy-constrained nodes such as the Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices is presented in [8]. In [9], the efficacy of the SKG from RSS variations is investigated by using an extensive real-world measurement data-set. The authors concluded that a higher KGR can be achieved in a more dynamic environment. The SKG in an indoor Gaussian channel is considered in [10], where good KRP and BMP performance is achieved while trading-off the KGR. A low-complexity key generation method is proposed [11], which investigates the problem of optimal-time allocation in channel estimation stage to maximize the KGR. A novel scheme for SKG between two multi-antenna legitimate nodes is proposed in [12] which aims at enhancing the KGR. Recently, a

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Fig. 1: Considered system model.

Complex Impulse Response (CIR) based quantization for secret keys using BPSK and QPSK modulation schemes in 2×2 , 4×4 , and 16×16 MIMO-OFDM systems is presented for Gaussian and Rayleigh distributed channels [13].

Channel quantization is one of the primary SKG stages. The quantizers can be mainly regarded as lossy or lossless quantizers [9]. The lossless quantizers exploit all channel samples for SKG which is unlike the lossy quantizers that exploit only a few selective samples. Lossy quantizers usually lack in KGR performance while they provide a gain in BMP and KRP performance. Another classification of quantizers is uniform and non-uniform quantizers. In [4], uniform and non-uniform quantization strategies for SKG are compared for LC SKG algorithm and a thorough analysis in terms of KGR, BMP, and KRP is conducted. An adaptive quantization method is proposed in [14] that is seen to achieve high KGR at the cost of high system complexity. To characterize the channel fluctuations with reference to multiple thresholds, a novel metric named Average Contiguous Duration (ACD) is proposed in [15]. Based on this metric, a quantization scheme for SKG is proposed in [16] that is shown to provide high KRP while maintaining the KGR and BMP performance.

This work proposes a novel Moving-Window Wrapped-Envelope SKG (MWWE-SKG) algorithm for generating secret keys from envelope samples of a Rice fading channel. The proposed algorithm aims at simultaneously enhancing KGR, BMP, and KRP performance of the extracted secret key bits. The main contributions of this work are listed as follows.

- A novel MWWE-SKG algorithm is proposed that exploits first-order statistics of a sliding window of channel samples for extracting key-bits from each window by processing a circularly wrapped channel envelope.
- Performance of the proposed algorithm is extensively analyzed in terms of BMP, KGR, and KRP. The influence of Rice K -factor and channel correlation coefficient on KGR, BMP, and KRP is investigated.
- A comparative analysis of the proposed algorithm with other notable algorithms is conducted.

This work is organized as follows. Section II presents the considered PLS system model, fading channel, and reciprocal channel sample generation procedure. Section III discusses the proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm. In Section IV, results and discussion is presented. Section V, concludes the work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In the considered system model, the legitimate communication nodes named Alice and Bob communicated

through main channel while a passive eavesdropper named Eve is present, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The reciprocal channels between Alice and Bob are represented by h_{ab} and h_{ba} . The Eves channels with Alice and Bob is represented by h_{ae} and h_{be} , respectively. The channels are modeled as Rice fading channels. The Eve is assumed to be located as multiple wavelengths apart from legitimate nodes, Alice and Bob, such that the Eve's channels are uncorrelated to the main channels (i.e., Eve encounters independent fading). In every coherence time frame, Alice and Bob estimate their channels by transmitting prob/training signals. The Alice's and Bob's channels, i.e., h_{ab} and h_{ba} , are reciprocal within a coherence time slot [9]. However, in practice, the difference in hardware noise conditions and other factors cause difference in the channel measurements. This difference in the channels can be modeled by Gauss Markov model [17] as

$$h_{ba} = \rho h_{ab} + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

where $\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is Gaussian-distributed error/difference in the channels and $\rho \in [0, 1]$ represents the correlation coefficient between the reciprocal channels h_{ab} and h_{ba} . The output signal received at Alice/Bob is shown as

$$y_{(\cdot)} = \sqrt{P_T} h_{(\cdot)} d^{-\alpha/2} x + n_{(\cdot)}, \quad (2)$$

where x is the transmit probe signal, P_T is the transmit power, α represents the path-loss exponent, d is the separation between Alice and Bob, and $n_{(\cdot)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_n^2)$ is the Gaussian-distributed error. The subscript (\cdot) takes label ab or ba for Alice-to-Bob and Bob-to-Alice communications.

The SNR at legitimate nodes (i.e., Alice and Bob) can be represented as

$$\gamma_{(\cdot)} = \frac{P_T |h_{(\cdot)}|^2 d^{-\alpha}}{\sigma^2}. \quad (3)$$

For unit noise variance, change in SNR represent the change in squared channel magnitude. The channels are modeled as Rice fading channels [18]. The Probability Distribution Function (PDF) of the Rice distributed channel magnitude can be expressed as

$$p(r) = \frac{2(K+1)r}{\Omega} \exp\left(-K - \frac{(K+1)r^2}{\Omega}\right) I_0\left(2\sqrt{\frac{K(K+1)}{\Omega}}r\right), \quad (4)$$

where r represents magnitude of complex channel envelope as $r = |h_{(\cdot)}|$, the Rice fading factor K represents the ratio between dominant/Line-of-Sight (LoS) and other (scattered) paths, Ω represents the total power, $I_0(\cdot)$ represents the modified Bessel function of first-kind and 0th order. For $K = 0$, the Rice fading deduces to Rayleigh fading, while for $K \rightarrow \infty$, it represents no fading case. In the proposed SKG scheme, described in the following section, the channel magnitude/envelope $|h_{(\cdot)}|$ is taken as Rice distributed which is used for SKG.

Fig. 2: Operation of proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm

III. PROPOSED MWWE-SKG ALGORITHM

The proposed SKG algorithm named MWWE-SKG is presented in Algorithm 1. The maximum and minimum channel magnitudes are r_{\max} and r_{\min} , respectively. The proposed algorithm operates for multi-level channel quantization, while the discussion and illustrations are presented for an example case of $M = 4$ levels. Employing uniform quantization scheme, all quantization intervals Q_i have an equal amplitude span L . We take a sliding window of channel samples w_s , where s is the window index. The overlap between the adjacent overlapped windows is O samples, where N is the total number of channel samples. The channels are modeled as Rice fading channels. An example Rice fading envelope with illustration expressing the basic working principle of the proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm is provided in Fig. 2.

The proposed algorithm begins with initialization of basic system parameters, e.g., sample count N , sliding window size w_s , window shift step-size z , etc. Subsequently, the algorithm proceeds with estimating the system and channel parameters such as noise power $\hat{\sigma}_n^2$, Rice fading factor \hat{K} , and channel variance $V_{(\cdot)} \sim (0 \sim V_{\max})$. The secret key extraction procedure typically involves four key steps: channel probing, quantization, information reconciliation, and privacy amplification [6].

Channel probing is a basic step that measures the channel response at both the legitimate communication terminals. The main channels h_{ab} and h_{ba} are estimated by Bob and Alice by transmitting time duplexed probe/training signals, respectively. For this study, the channel samples are drawn randomly from Rice distribution for the preset fading severity parameters and correlation conditions using the model presented in (1)-(4). After channel probing, the quantization is performed that transforms the continuous and analog channel measurements into secret key bits. Quantization in SKG algorithms is different from that performed in classical analog-to-digital converters, as it involves additional step of suitable samples selection (i.e., selective samples are used instead of using all the samples). The algorithm determine the count of quantization levels M to be used depending upon the estimated

SNR condition $\gamma = \frac{P_s}{P_n}$, where P_s is signal power and P_n is noise power. The channel dynamic range lies over the interval from r_{\min} to r_{\max} . The interval of each quantization level for uniform quantization strategy can be determined as, $L = (r_{\max} - r_{\min})/M$. The thresholds for separating the quantization intervals can be computed as $r_i = iL, i \in (0 \sim M + 1)$ for quantization levels. From N channel samples, a sliding window takes selective samples W_s of w_s samples, where s represents the window index. Over the iterations, the window slides in overlapped fashion. For each iteration, w_s samples are selected and window slides for z samples, i.e., the overlap of window for current and previous iteration is O samples, see Fig. 2. In step 9, the algorithm computes first-order statistics of the current samples window, i.e., mean μ_p and variance v_p of sliding window W_s . Based on these statistics, the preliminary quantization level index m is determined. Subsequently, a circular shift proportional to the variance of the current sample window ϕ in m is introduced. In Fig. 2, the working principle of MWWE-SKG algorithm is shown for a 4-level uniform quantization strategy. The quantized channel magnitude axis (i.e., vertical axis over discrete levels) is considered circularly wrapped, i.e., the shift in quantization index is unwrap to determine the final selected quantization interval, see steps 12 to 14 of the algorithm. The preset binary sequences associated to the selected quantization levels are concatenated into $\mathcal{K}_{(\cdot)}$, which after repeating steps 7 to 18 over the entire range of available channel samples represents the extracted secret key-bits. After each iteration the window slides a preset amount of u samples (it can be adapted according to channel fading condition). Finally, the information reconciliation step reconciles the extracted key bits at both legitimate communication terminals for the rectification of any mismatches. In this work, Bose-Chaudhuri-Hocquenghem (BCH) codes based information reconciliation is performed to obtain the results [19].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the conducted simulation results are presented. The effect of variations in reciprocal channels correlation coefficient, Rice K fading factor, and window overlap on the KGR, BMP, and KRP are analyzed. The results of the proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm are compared with Mathur's Level crossing SKG (LC-SKG) algorithm [7]. The proposed multilevel MWWE-SKG algorithm outperforms its counterpart in terms of KGR, BMP, and KRP performance.

A. KGR

In Fig. 3, the KGR performance analysis is conducted. The proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm can be seen to provide superior performance in terms of KGR compared to that provided by LC-SKG algorithm proposed in [7]. The effect of change in reciprocal channels' correlation coefficient ρ on KGR is presented in Fig. 3 (a). For obtaining this plot, the Rice factor is set as $K = 1$. An increase in ρ causes an increase in the KGR performance of both MWWE-SKG and LC-SKG algorithms, which is mainly caused due to the information reconciliation stage. The observed performance gain by the

Algorithm 1: Proposed SKG MWWE-SKG Algorithm**Initialize/Estimate Parameters**

- 1 Sample count N , window size w_s , window shift z , index $u=0$.
- 2 Estimate noise power $\hat{\sigma}_n^2$, Rice factor \hat{K} , and channel variance $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_{(\cdot)} \sim (0 \sim \mathcal{V}_{\max})$.
- 3 Measure/generate channel samples $|\mathbf{h}_{(\cdot)}|$, (i.e., Rice fading).
- 4 Determine number of quantization levels $M \propto \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_n^2}$.
- 5 Calculate channel dynamic range $L = \frac{r_{\max} - r_{\min}}{M}$.
- 6 Calculate thresholds: $r_i = iL$, where $i \in (0 \sim M + 1)$.

Sliding window: Key extraction

- 7 **for** $s=1 : S$ **do**
- 8 $\mathbf{W}_s \leftarrow \mathbf{h}_{(\cdot)}[u + 1 : u + w_s]$
- 9 Estimate window mean: $\mu_s \leftarrow \text{mean}(\mathbf{W}_s)$,
and variance: $v_s \leftarrow \text{var}(\mathbf{W}_s)$
- 10 $m \leftarrow$ Quantization level index of μ_p .
- 11 **Introduce circular shift in index m as**
Compute magnitude of shift

$$\phi \leftarrow \begin{cases} m \pm (M - 1) & ; & 0 \leq v_s \leq \frac{\mathcal{V}_{\max}}{M - 1}, \\ \vdots & ; & \vdots \\ m \pm 1 & ; & \frac{M - 2}{M - 1} \mathcal{V}_{\max} < v_s < \mathcal{V}_{\max}. \end{cases}$$
- 12 **Apply shift and unwrap quantization level index ϕ**
While $\phi > M$ **do**
13 $\phi \leftarrow \phi - M$
14 **end**
15 $\alpha \leftarrow$ Preset binary sequence of quantization level ϕ .
16 $\mathcal{K}_{(\cdot)} \leftarrow [\mathcal{K}_{(\cdot)} \alpha]$
17 Slide window: $u \leftarrow u + z$
18 **End for**
19 Reconcile $\mathcal{K}_{(\cdot)}$ between Alice and Bob.

proposed algorithm establishes it a more suitable choice for SKG, particularly for low correlation ρ conditions.

The effect of change in Rice K -factor on the KGR performance is plotted in Fig. 3(b). The proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm can be seen to achieve higher KGR than that provided by LC algorithm [7]. This result is obtained for correlation coefficient and window overlap set as $\rho = 0.9$ and $O = 5$, respectively. For LC-SKG algorithm, the variations in K initially causes an increase in KGR, while for the range approximately beyond $K = 2.5$, the plot becomes flat. However, for the proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm, the variations in K does not vastly influence KGR. This demonstrates that, without any loss in KGR along the variations in K , the proposed algorithm provides better performance in BMP and KRP performance.

The effect of window overlap O relative to the total window size w_s on KGR performance is plotted in Fig. 3 (c). This result is obtained for correlation $\rho = 0.9$ and Rice factor $K = 1$. It can be observed that the change in the rate of window overlap vastly influences the KGR performance. For a given number of channel samples, a higher window overlap makes more number of available windows which directly increases the KGR. For $W_s = 10$, an increase in window overlap from

Fig. 3: Effect of variations in correlation coefficient ρ , Rice fading factor K , and Window size W_s on KGR performance in (a), (b), and (c), respectively.

$O = 3$ to 7 provides an improvement of 0.29 in KGR, see Fig. 3 (c).

B. BMP

The BMP performance with respect to variations in correlation coefficient ρ , Rice K factor, and window size w_s is conducted in this subsection. The proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm promises less BMP than that provided by LC algorithm [7] over all correlation conditions, see Fig. 4 (a). For obtaining this plot, the Rice fading factor was taken fixed as $K = 1$. An increase in ρ causes a decrease in bit mismatch. In adverse correlations conditions (i.e., $\rho < 0.5$), the proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm provides a significant gain in BMP performance compared to LC algorithm. The effect of variations in channel fading conditions on BMP performance is shown in Fig. 4 (b), while the channel correlation is fixed at $\rho = 0.9$. An increase in K causes a decrease in BMP, which is favourable. The proposed MWWE-SKG algorithm achieves less BMP than that provided by LC algorithm [7].

The results in Fig. 4(c) are obtained for correlation $\rho = 0.9$ and Rice factor $K = 1$. The change in window overlap O influences all the performance metrics. When the window overlap increases from $O = 3$ to 7 samples for all window sizes, the BMP decreases, see Fig. 4 (c). This is because the first- and second-order statistics of a reasonably overlapped sliding window (with reference to its size) stay correlated. On the other hand, for an overlap of $O = 3$ samples, the BMP is adverse, as observable in Fig. 4 (c). A 50% window overlap is observed to provide a good performance trade off.

C. Randomness

The KRP performance in this subsection is evaluated using National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) statistical test suite. The p-value of selected NIST tests are demonstrated in Table 1. When the window overlap O increases, the generated secret key bits are seen to demonstrate less random KRP. This is because a larger overlap between adjacent windows causes similar and correlated samples (similar statistics) in the adjacent windows which makes them more likely to map on the same quantization interval. The suitable trade off between KRP, KGR, and BMP performance is observed at 50% window overlap setting. A

Fig. 4: Effect of variations in correlation coefficient ρ , Rice fading factor K , and Window size W_s on BMP performance in (a), (b), and (c), respectively.

Table 1. NIST tests for KRP evaluation

Randomness NIST Test Suite (P-value)				
Test Name	P-value of LC Algorithm	P-value of proposed MWWE-SKG Algorithm $O=3$	P-value of proposed MWWE-SKG Algorithm $O=5$	P-value of proposed MWWE-SKG Algorithm $O=7$
Frequency Test	0.5336	1	0.93	0.676
Block Frequency Test	0.02	1	0.9	0.653
DFT Test	0.36	0.765	0.67	0.456
Cumulative Sum Forward	0.165	0.432	0.343	0.235
Cumulative Sum Reverse	0.165	0.432	0.343	0.23
Entropy Test	0.02	0.547	0.443	0.355
Rank Test	0.93	1	0.93	0.673
Longer Runs of Ones	0.2	0.637	0.535	0.472
Run Test	0.5336	0.86	0.76	0.53

comparative analysis of the proposed MWWE-SKG Algorithm with LC Algorithm [7] regarding KRP performance is also demonstrated in Table 1, where the proposed algorithm outperforms its counterpart.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel algorithm named MWWE-SKG has been proposed that exploits the first-order statistics of the moving window of channel samples for effectively determining a quantization interval for each window for key-bits extraction from over a circularly wrapped channel envelope. Performance of the proposed algorithm has been extensively analyzed in terms of BMP, KGR, and KRP. The impact of variations in the Rice K-factor, channel correlation coefficient, window size, and window overlap rate has been investigated. A wider overlap causes an increase in KGR performance at the expense of KRP and BMP performance, while a 50% overlap has been observed as optimal for achieving a good trade-off between all the performance metrics. Furthermore, a comparison of the proposed scheme with its counterpart in the literature has also been conducted, where the offered performance gain establishes the value of the proposed scheme.

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